

A NEW TRIGGER MECHANISM FOR CRUSHING SQUARE CFRP TUBES

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ABSTRACT

A low initial peak crushing force or a high crushing force efficiency of a vehicle crashworthy structure are desirable to minimise the occupants' injury during a vehicle crushing deceleration. The aim of this study is to reduce the initial peak crushing and increase the energy dissipation of square CFRP tubes and aluminium sheet-wrapped square CFRP tubes. Manufactured platens with cutting blades were employed as new external trigger and energy dissipated mechanisms. These platens with cutting blades were specially designed to simultaneously cut and crush CFRP tubes to reduce the initial peak crushing force and achieve stable mixed deformation modes (cutting and progressive crushing). The results of tubes cut and crushed by platens with blades are compared with those of tubes crushed by only flat platens. It was found that CFRP tubes or aluminium sheet-wrapped CFRP tubes cut and crushed by platens with blades have a low peak crushing force, a high crushing force efficiency and a large mean crushing force and a high energy absorption compared with those for tubes under only crushing by flat loading platens.

1 INTRODUCTION

Thin-walled tubular structures have been widely used as energy absorbers in many applications such as transportation vehicles. These tubular structures have excellent capabilities to dissipate the impact energy during a crash. One important crushing parameter needs to be considered during a vehicle crash is the crushing force efficiency (CFE), which is the ratio of mean crushing force (MCF) to peak crushing force (PCF). A high value of crushing force efficiency is desirable to reduce the vehicle passenger's injury during a crash. Therefore, Researchers extensively investigated the effect of trigger mechanisms on the crushing performance of tubes in order to reduce the initial impact load (first peak crushing force) and protect vehicle occupants during a crash.

Hussein et al. [1, 2] studied experimentally square CFRP tubes and tubes externally wrapped by one layer, two layers and three layers of aluminium sheets subjected to axial crushing by flat loading platens. It was found that the peak crushing force of CFR tubes and aluminium sheet-wrapped CFRP tubes increased with the number of layers of aluminium sheet. On the other hand, the crushing force efficiency (CFE) was not significantly influenced by the number of layers of the aluminium sheet. The CFE was 55% for CFRP tubes and 50%, 50% and 54% for CFRP tubes wrapped by one layer, two layers and three layers of aluminium sheet respectively [2]. Hull [3] studied experimentally the effect of a chamfer trigger mechanism on the axial crushing behaviour of circular glass fibre and carbon fibre reinforced plastic tubes. It was found that the composite tube without a trigger mechanism failed by three fundamentally different modes: Euler buckling, shell buckling and brittle fracture. By using a 45° chamfer trigger mechanism, it was observed that the tubes failed by a progressive crushing mode. Hull

[3] also found that the peak crushing force (PCF) of tubes dropped because of a chamfer trigger mechanism.

Sigalas et al. [4] also studied the effect of a chamfer trigger mechanism on the failure mode of glass fibre/epoxy tubes with a wide range of chamfer angles from 10° to 90° . It was noticed that the chamfered part was first bent outwards and then crack developed to break chamfered part outwards. The peak crushing forces of tubes were found to decrease with the angle of chamfer while there was no influence of a chamfer angle on the mean crushing force of composite tubes. Farley and Jones [5] and Mamalis et al. [6] found that a trigger mechanism helped to initiate a stable crushing failure mode. It was observed that the composite tubes might fail catastrophically without a trigger mechanism. However, when introducing a trigger mechanism, the deformation mode changed to a progressive failure with fragmentation.

Huang and Wang [7] studied experimentally the crushing response of circular and square CFRP tubes with and without using a bevel trigger mechanism. It was found that using a bevel trigger could control the position of initial failure to make tubes failed by a stable progressive deformation mode instead of a catastrophic failure. Huang and Wang [7] also found that the SEA of tubes without a trigger was 66.48 J/g while it was 62.73 J/g for tubes with a bevel trigger. In contrast, the crushing force efficiency (CFE) of tubes with a trigger mechanism was higher than that of tubes without a trigger mechanism. A subsequent study by Huang and Wang [8] was examined a crown trigger mechanism which was introduced at one end of the CFRP circular tubes. The SEA of CFRP tube with a crown trigger was 62.06 J/g, which was very similar to the SEA of CFRP tube with a bevel trigger (62.73 J/g) [7]. On the other hand, the CFE of tubes with the crown trigger was approximately 171.5% and 21.2% higher than the CFE for tubes without a trigger mechanism and tubes with a bevel trigger respectively.

Palanivelu et al. [9] compared two different triggering mechanisms; 45° chamfering and 90° tulips that introduced in unidirectional E-glass fibre/polyester tubes subjected to axial quasi-static compressive loads. It was observed that there was no significant difference between these two triggering mechanisms on the deformation modes of the composite tubes. Eshkoor et al. [10] analysed the crashworthiness behaviour of natural plain-woven silk/epoxy composite square tubes with no trigger, tulip trigger and external metallic trigger. The external metallic trigger was four rectangular metal pieces and was fixed in the middle of tube walls. The four metal pieces of trigger reduced the initial peak crushing force and changed the deformation mode of tubes from a catastrophic mode to a progressive failure mode. It was also found that trigger mechanisms had no effect on the mean crushing force, energy absorption and specific energy absorption of silk/epoxy tubes. Hussein et al. [11-13] used platens with different blade profiles to cut and crush CFRP tubes and aluminium sheet-wrapped CFRP tubes to cause more damage to 90° fibres that are perpendicular to the applied loads. It was found that the mean crushing force, energy absorption and specific energy absorption of tubes crushed by platens with blades increased compared with those of CFRP tubes crushed by a flat platen. However, the effect of using platens with blades on the peak crushing force and crushing force efficiency of CFRP tubes and aluminium sheet-wrapped CFRP tubes has not been comprehensively analysed.

This study will focus on analysing the effect of platens with cutting blades on the initial peak crushing force, mean crushing force and crushing force efficiency of CFRP tubes and aluminium sheet-wrapped CFRP tubes that investigated by Hussein et al. [11-13]. An axial quasi-static compressive load at a constant velocity of 0.05 mm/s was applied to CFRP tubes and aluminium sheet-wrapped CFRP tubes. Loading platens with different blade profiles were used to cut through the tubes while axially crushing them at the same time. Corresponding tube structures were also axially compressed by flat loading platens for comparison purposes. One of the potential applications of this current research is in the design of tubular structures where a triggering mechanism is introduced to reduce the initial peak force and increase the energy absorption [11].

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

The square CFRP tubes were made from 3K twill weave carbon fabric ($0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}$) and SE84LV epoxy. The tube walls consisted of 8 fabric layers with a tube inner side length, tube height and wall thickness are 50 mm, 50 mm and 2.1 mm respectively. The mechanical properties of square CFRP tubes were presented in articles published by Hussein et al. [1, 11]. They conducted tensile tests on five CFRP coupons to determine the mechanical properties of the square CFRP tube, see Ref. [1] for more details. Engineering stress-strain curves of the five CFRP test coupons are shown in Fig. 1(a). Average longitudinal modulus of elasticity of all coupons was 58.8 GPa, average Poisson's ratio was 0.1, and average ultimate tensile stress was 576.6 MPa, at an approximate strain of 0.01.

The thin aluminium sheet was made by Fujifilm Company and the sheet model is Brillia HD LH-PJE offset printing plate with a thickness of 0.25 mm for a single layer. See Ref. [11] for more details about the material properties of aluminium sheet that calculated from tensile tests. Fig. 1(b) shows the engineering stress-strain curves of the five aluminium sheet coupons. The average yield stress and ultimate stress of the aluminium sheet were approximately 197 MPa and 201 MPa respectively. Aluminium sheet was bonded to CFRP tube walls by using Araldite 420 (A/B) epoxy.

Figure 1: (a) Typical engineering stress-strain curves of CFRP coupons from tensile tests [1]; (b) typical engineering stress-strain curves of aluminium sheet coupons from tensile tests [11].

In order to initiate cutting in the tubular structures, high tensile steel (AISI 4140) was used to manufacture platens with four cutting blades. Fig. 2 presents one representative platen with blades and the blade dimensions that used by Hussein et al. [13] to find the best platen with blades that cause more damage to CFRP tubes (for more details, refer to Ref [13]). A 250 kN MTS universal testing machine was used to apply an axial compressive load to the tubes at a constant velocity of 0.05 mm/s. During testing, the lower platen of the MTS machine moved upwards to crush the tubes and the upper platen was fixed.

Photographs of representative specimens that crushed by flat platens in the study [11] and cut and crushed by a platen with blades in the same study [11] are shown in Fig. 3. For more specimens photographs, refer to Ref. [11]. Specimens that evaluated their crushing parameters in this study were square CFRP tubes (C), one layer of aluminium sheet-wrapped CFRP tubes (1AC), two layers of aluminium sheet-wrapped CFRP tubes (2AC) and three layers of aluminium sheet-wrapped CFRP tubes (3AC). These specimens were crushed by using flat platens at both the top and bottom of specimens as presented in Fig. 3(c). Another group of specimens was CFRP tubes with notches (CNB), one layer of aluminium sheet-wrapped CFRP tubes with notches (1ACNB), two layers of aluminium sheet-wrapped CFRP tubes with notches (2ACNB) and three layers of aluminium sheet-wrapped CFRP tubes with notches (3ACNB). "N" and "B" in the specimen designation stand for notches and blades respectively. These specimens were placed between a top fixed platen with blades and a movable flat platen at the bottom as shown in Fig. 3(f).

The magnitudes of crushing parameters were calculated directly from the force-displacement curves. Peak crushing force (PCF) is defined as the first maximum load. Mean crushing force (MCF) was calculated as the average force over a displacement from 2 mm to 40 mm. Crushing force efficiency (CFE) is defined as the ratio of the MCF to PCF. Energy absorption (EA) is the energy dissipated by the test specimens during the crushing process. It was determined from the area under the force-displacement curves over a displacement from 0 mm to 40 mm. Specific energy absorption (SEA) is the dissipated energy divided by the crushed structure's mass (m). All test results are summarised in Table 1.

Figure 2: (a) A representative platen with four blades; (b) a sketch of 45° inclined blade (B3) (all dimensions are in mm) [11].

Figure 3: Photographs of representative specimens to be crushed by flat platens: (a) a CFRP tube (C); (b) one layer of aluminium sheet-wrapped CFRP tube (1AC); (c) illustration of test set-up for specimens crushed by flat platens; photographs of representative specimens with notches to be crushed by a platen with blades: (a) a CFRP tube (CNB); (b) one layer of aluminium sheet-wrapped CFRP tube (1ACNB); (c) illustration of test set-up for specimens cut and crushed by a platen with blades [11].

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Hussein et al. [1, 2, 11-13] found that the deformation mode of CFRP tubes that crushed by flat platens or platens with cutting blades was a combination of splaying progressive and transverse shearing (fragmentation) mode. There were also splitting at corners of tested specimens. For tubes under cut and crush, there were additional cuts in the middle of tubes by blades. Fig. 4 shows the deformation mode of CFRP tubes and aluminium sheet-wrapped CFRP tubes under crushing by flat platens and a platen with cutting blades. It was concluded that there was no difference in the deformation mode of CFRP tubes with using various platens with blades. Furthermore, all CFRP tubes' walls were cut by the different blades [13]. For more details of microscopic failure mechanisms of tubes under axial crushing by flat platens and platens with cutting blades, see Refs. [1, 2, 11-13]. Using the platen with blades to crush the specimens exhibited more stable deformation mode than the specimens crushed by a flat platen. CFRP plies were ground by using blades due to apply a shear stress to CFRP plies after cutting them with blade tips. The wider blades were 45° inclined blades caused more damage to the 90° fibres with wider cutting track and acted similarly to trigger mechanisms [13].

Figure 4: Final deformation modes of (a) a CFRP tube crushed by flat platens (C), (b) three layers of aluminium sheet-wrapped CFRP tube crushed by flat platens (3AC); (c) a CFRP tube cut and crushed by a platen with cutting blades (CNB3); (d) three layers of aluminium sheet-wrapped CFRP tube cut and crushed by a platen with blades (3ACNB3) [13].

The crushing force is another important parameter was considered to evaluate the effectiveness of using cutting blades to improve the crushing behaviour of CFRP tubes. Fig. 5 shows the force-displacement curves of specimens under only axial crushing by flat platens and specimens under both cutting and crushing by a platen with cutting blades. All crushing parameters such as peak crushing force (PCF), mean crushing force (MCF), crushing force efficiency (CFE), energy absorption (EA) and specific energy absorption (SEA) of tested specimens are listed in Table 1. It is evident from Table 1 that specimens cut and crushed by a platen with 45° inclined blades had higher mean crushing forces (MCF) and energy absorption (EA) than the MCF and EA of specimens cut and crushed by other platens with blades. The maximum values of energy absorption and specific energy absorption (SEA) for tested specimens were 1950 J and 70 J/g respectively for CFRP tube (CNB3) and 3216 J and 59 J/g respectively for aluminium sheet-wrapped CFRP tube (3ACNB3). On the other hand, for specimens crushed by flat platens, the EA and SEA were 1882 J and 60 J/g respectively for CFRP tubes (C) and 2754 J and 48 J/g respectively for aluminium sheet-wrapped CFRP tube (3AC).

A low value of peak crushing force (PCF) or a high value of crushing force efficiency (CFE) of a structure are desirable because such a structure would minimise the occupants' injury (if this structure was used as a vehicle crash structure). CFE is the ratio of mean crushing force (MCF) to peak crushing force (PCF). Fig. 6(a) presents a graphical comparison of the peak crushing forces of tubes subjected to axial crush by flat loading platens and tubes subjected to axial cut and crush by platens with different blade profiles. It is clear from Fig. 6(a) that the platens with blades acted as trigger mechanisms to reduce the peak crushing forces while increasing the mean crushing forces of CFRP tubes with and without aluminium sheets wrapping. The peak crushing force of aluminium sheet-

wrapped CFRP tubes crushed by a platen with cutting blades decreased by up to 64% of that for tubes crushed by flat platens. For example, the PCF of 3ACNB4 was 76.5 kN while it was 125.4 kN for the specimen (3AC).

Figure 5: Force-displacement curves of CFRP tubes and aluminium sheet-wrapped CFRP tubes crushed by (a) flat loading platens; (b) a platen with cutting blades [11].

Specimen designation	Details	Blade type	PCF (kN)	MCF (kN)	CFE (%)	EA (J)	SEA (J/g)
C	CFRP square tubes	Flat platens	86.0	47.3	55	1882	60
CNB1		3 mm straight blades	65.7	48.9	74	1897	67
CNB2		5 mm straight blades	59	47.2	80	1872	69
CNB3		45° inclined blades	69.05	49.3	72	1950	70
CNB4		60° inclined blades	57.3	48.3	84	1908	67
CNB5		75° inclined blades	58.2	48.9	84	1929	67
1AC	One layer of aluminium sheet-wrapped CFRP tubes	Flat platens	110.1	55.6	51	2223	59
1ACNB3		45° inclined blades	97.75	57.7	59	2298	66
2AC	Two layer of aluminium sheet-wrapped CFRP tubes	Flat platens	120.3	58.8	49	2348	51
2ACNB3		45° inclined blades	107.9	65.9	61	2603	59
3AC	Three layer of aluminium sheet-wrapped CFRP tubes	Flat platens	125.4	69.8	56	2754	48
3ACNB1		3 mm straight blades	110.9	80.6	73	3198	53
3ACNB2		5 mm straight blades	93	74	80	2908	52
3ACNB3		45° inclined blades	123.4	81.1	66	3216	59
3ACNB4		60° inclined blades	76.5	73.6	96	2896	51
3ACNB5		75° inclined blades	100.1	75.2	75	2937	50

Table 1 Summary of test results [1, 11, 13].

It was noted from Table 1 that tubes cut and crushed by platens with blades have higher CFE than tubes crushed by flat platens. Fig. 6(b) shows a graphical comparison of the crushing force efficiencies (CFE) for CFRP tubes and tubes externally wrapped by aluminium sheet under crushing by flat platens compared with those tubes under cutting and crushing by platens with different blade profiles. The high value of CFE for tubes under cutting and crushing (Fig. 6(b)) is another evident that platens

with cutting blades acted as new trigger mechanisms. That was because of the platen with cutting blades caused to increase the mean crushing force of CFRP tubes and tubes wrapped externally by aluminium sheets. Thus, the platen with blades acted as well as energy dissipated mechanisms. The tubes cut and crushed by platens with blades had higher CFE compared with those for tubes crushed by only flat loading platens. The maximum crushing force efficiency was 96% for three layers of aluminium sheet-wrapped CFRP tube (3ACNB4), cut and crushed by a platen with 60° inclined blades while it was 56% for (3AC), crushed by flat platens. Thus, the maximum increase of CFE of tubes under both cutting and crushing was 71% compared with tubes under only crushing.

Figure 6: Graphical comparisons of (a) peak crushing force (PCF); (b) crushing force efficiency (CFE). Tubes crushed by flat platens are (C, 1AC, 2AC, 3AC). Tubes cut and crushed by platens with different blade profiles are (CNB1, CNB2, CNB3, CNB4, CNB5, 1ACNB3, 2ACNB3, 3ACNB1, 3ACNB2, 3ACNB3, 3ACNB4, 3ACNB5).

4 CONCLUSIONS

CFRP tubes and aluminium sheet-wrapped CFRP tubes were cut and crushed by using platens with different blade profiles. The deformation mode of CFRP tubes under axial crushing only or both cutting and crushing was a combination of progressive splaying and transverse shearing mode. There were additional cuts in the middle of tubes that cut and crushed by platens with cutting blades. It was concluded that the platens with blades acted as trigger mechanisms to reduce the peak crushing force of tubes. The platens with blades also acted as energy dissipated mechanisms to cause the increase of the energy absorption of tubes by mixing two deformation modes (cutting and progressive crushing). The tubes cut and crushed by platen with blades had a high mean crushing force, low peak crushing force, high crushing force efficiency, large energy absorption and high specific energy absorption compared with those for tubes crushed by flat loading platens.

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